

Photochemical and Thermal Transformations of S-Benzoyl-O-alkyl Xanthates

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The reaction of benzoyl chloride with different potassium-O-alkyl xanthates (*n*-propyl, *iso*-propyl, *n*-butyl) around 0° afforded good yields of corresponding S-benzoyl-O-alkyl xanthates. The structure of these aroyl xanthates were consistent with the spectral data. Aroyl xanthates have been reported to be resistant to photolysis. It has, however, been observed in the present investigation that the fragmentation of these S-benzoyl-O-alkyl xanthates does occur on prolonged photolysis. Irradiation of these xanthates in benzene solution with mercury lamp for 60-70 hr resulted in the formation of benzoyl disulfide. Thermal decomposition around 250° for 15 min gave benzoyl disulfide, corresponding ester and carbon disulfide.

PHOTOCHEMICAL and thermal transformations of a few acyl xanthates have been reported by Barton *et al*¹, who observed that alkane and aryl-alkanecarbonyl xanthates are decomposed by light. Thus for example, irradiation of O-ethyl-S-phenyl acetyl xanthate in benzene solution under reflux gave S-benzoyl-O-ethyl xanthate in high yield. It has been suggested that the photolysis of acyl xanthates proceed through a free radical pathway involving the initial fragmentation of a C-S bond, resulting in the formation of acyl and xanthate radicals.

A similar type of fragmentation has been reported in the photolysis of several acyl xanthates², phthaloyl dioxanthates^{3,4}, phthalic bis dithiocarbamic anhydride⁴, O-alkyl-S-phthalyl xanthates⁵ and dithiocarbamoyl phthalides⁶.

S-benzoyl and S-*p*-chloro benzoyl-O-ethyl xanthates were reported¹ to be resistant to photolysis in boiling benzene or toluene due to the stability of ArCO radical formed during photolysis.

The object of the present investigation was to examine both the photochemical and thermal transformations of a few aroyl xanthates, with a view to studying the nature of the products formed in these reactions and the mode of fragmentation. In this connection we have studied the reaction of benzoyl chloride with different potassium-O-alkyl xanthates.

Treatment of an acetone solution of benzoyl chloride around 0° with potassium-O-alkyl xanthates gave S-benzoyl-O-alkyl xanthates (Ia-c) in good yield.

The structural assignment of Ia-c were consistent with the spectral data. The ir spectrum of these

aroyl xanthates showed prominent bands at 1700 and 1270 cm⁻¹ due to the presence of C=O and C=S groups, respectively. The uv spectrum showed a weak absorption band at 410 nm, characteristic of aroyl xanthates.

Photolysis of the xanthates (Ia-c) in dry benzene for 60-70 hr with a mercury lamp in a pyrex flask gave a gummy solid from which only benzoyl disulfide could be isolated. A probable mechanism consistent with the formation of this product is shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1.

The free-radical pathway involving a C(S)-S bond fission resulting in the free radical II and subsequent dimerisation explains the formation of III. Benzoyl disulfide thus formed has been reported to be resistant to photolysis⁷. However,

earlier workers have reported the formation of free-radicals due to the C(O)-S bond fission^{1,2}. Our attempts to isolate benzil from the reaction mixture were not successful, which indicates that the aroyl radical formed during the photolysis does not dimerise.

The thermal decomposition of aroyl xanthates have been reported to be much more complex^{1,7}. Thus, thermal decomposition of O-ethyl-S-benzoyl xanthate at 18 mm has been reported to give a mixture of benzoyl disulfide, ethyl benzoate, ethyl thiobenzoate, ethyl dithiobenzoate and tetraphenyl thiophene nonasulfide⁷. Barton *et al* have reported the thermal decomposition of acyl xanthates around 200° to give esters and carbon disulfide¹. A four membered cyclic transition state has been suggested for such decomposition^{1,8}. Pyrolysis of xanthates (Ia-c) around 250° for 15 min gave benzoyl disulfide, corresponding esters and carbon disulfide as shown in Scheme 1.

Experimental

IR spectra were recorded on Beckman IR-20 Infrared spectrophotometer and uv spectra were recorded on Specord UV spectrophotometer. Potassium-O-*n*-propyl xanthate, m.p. 230°, potassium-O-isopropyl xanthate, m.p. 274°, and potassium-O-*n*-butyl xanthate, m.p. 258° were prepared by known procedure⁹. TLC was run on silica gel using methylene chloride-petroleum ether (1 : 1) as eluent.

Reaction of benzoyl chloride with potassium-O-alkyl xanthate :

Ia : Benzoyl chloride (1.40 g ; 0.01 mole) was taken in acetone (20 ml) and to this was added potassium-O-*n*-propyl xanthate (1.74 g ; 0.01 mole) portion-wise with constant stirring at 0° during 30 min. Stirring was continued for additional 30 min at room temperature. Filtration of precipitated potassium chloride and removal of the solvent under vacuum gave a residue which was dissolved in methylene chloride (25 ml) and washed with 1% NaHCO₃ solution.

The methylene chloride extract was repeatedly washed with water and dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Removal of the solvent gave 2.26 g (94%) of S-benzoyl-O-*n*-propyl xanthate (Ia) as a yellow liquid, n_D^{20} 1.6010 ; uv : $\lambda_{\text{Max}}^{\text{Etanol}}$ 215 (ϵ , 13,740), 245 (ϵ , 19,200), 280 (ϵ , 10,260) and 410 nm (ϵ , 76) ; ir : 1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1270 cm⁻¹ (C=S). This xanthate was unstable and satisfactory analytical data were not secured for this compound.

Ib : Similarly, S-benzoyl-O-isopropyl xanthate (Ib) in 51% yield was obtained as a yellow liquid, n_D^{20} 1.5010 ; uv : $\lambda_{\text{Max}}^{\text{Etanol}}$ 215 (ϵ , 9,000), 245 (ϵ , 12,800), 290 (ϵ , 5,650) and 410 nm (ϵ , 39) ; ir : 1700 cm⁻¹

(C=O), 1380 cm⁻¹ ($-\text{HC} \begin{matrix} \text{CH}_3 \\ \text{CH}_3 \end{matrix}$), 1270 cm⁻¹ (C=S). (Found : C, 55.58 ; H, 5.27. C₁₁H₁₃O₂S₂ requires C, 55.0 ; H, 5.0%)

Ic : Similarly, S-benzoyl-O-*n*-butyl xanthate (Ic) in 56% yield was obtained as a yellow liquid n_D^{20} 1.5940 ; uv : $\lambda_{\text{Max}}^{\text{Etanol}}$ 215 (ϵ , 12,192), 250 (ϵ , 14,859), 285 (ϵ , 12,192) and 410 nm (ϵ , 96) ; ir : 1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O), 1270 cm⁻¹ (C=S).

This xanthate was unstable and satisfactory analytical data were not secured for this compound.

Photochemical transformation of S-benzoyl-O-alkyl xanthate :

Ia : A solution of the xanthate Ia (1.00 g) in dry benzene (A.R ; 35 ml) was irradiated for 70 hr with mercury lamp in a pyrex flask. Removal of the solvent gave a gummy solid. Trituration with petroleum ether resulted in 75 mg of benzoyl disulfide, m.p. 129° (m.m.p.)¹⁰. A solution of the xanthate Ia subjected to similar conditions in the absence of light did not show any appreciable change.

Similarly, the photolysis of Ib (1.00 g) and Ic (2.02 g) in benzene solution gave benzoyl disulfide as the only isolable product in yield 115 mg and 205 mg, respectively.

Thermal decomposition of S-benzoyl-O-alkylxanthate :

Ia : The xanthate Ia (3.50 g) was heated under continuous stream of nitrogen in an oil bath maintained at 250° for 15 min. The gaseous product was trapped by passing it in piperidine solution (in methylene chloride) which gave 1.30 g of piperidinium cyclopentamethylenedithiocarbamate, m.p. 169° (lit. m.p. 169°)⁸, corresponding to 36% yield of carbon disulfide. The residual brown mass was triturated with petroleum ether and the solid thus separated was filtered and recrystallised from a mixture of methylene chloride and petroleum ether to give 0.21 g of benzoyl disulfide, m.p. 129° (m.m.p.)¹⁰. The residual mass was hydrolysed with 10% aq. KOH to give 0.28 g of benzoic acid, m.p. 119° (m.m.p) corresponding to 16% yield of *n*-propylbenzoate.

Ib : Similarly, heating Ib (3.13 g) at 250° for 15 min gave 1.02 g of piperidinium cyclopentamethylenedithiocarbamate, m.p. 169°, corresponding to 34% yield of carbon disulfide, and 0.43 g of benzoyl disulfide, m.p. 129°. Hydrolysis of residual mass gave 0.360 g of benzoic acid, m.p. 119° corresponding to 17% yield of isopropylbenzoate.

Ic : Similarly, heating Ic (3.60 g) at 250° for 15 min gave 1.98 g of piperidinium cyclopentamethylenedithiocarbamate, m.p. 169° corresponding to 57% yield of carbon disulfide and 0.21 g of benzoyl disulfide, m.p. 129°. Hydrolysis of the residual mass gave 0.40 g of benzoic acid, m.p. 119° corresponding to 23% yield of *n*-butyl benzoate.

DARJI & SHAH : PHOTOCHEMICAL AND THERMAL TRANSFORMATIONS OF S-BENZOYL- ETC.

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